

AN EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE OF THE WILLIS-FORM EQUATIONS AND THE RELATED APPLICATIONS

Z.H. Xiang¹, R.W. Yao², H.X. Gao³, Y.X. Sun⁴ and X.D. Yuan⁵

¹ AML, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China,

xiangzhihai@tsinghua.edu.cn

² AML, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China,

yrw11@mails.tsinghua.edu.cn

³ AML, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China,

gaohx15@mails.tsinghua.edu.cn

⁴ AML, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China,

sunyx13@mails.tsinghua.edu.cn

⁵ AML, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing 100084, China,

yuanxd16@mails.tsinghua.edu.cn

Keywords: Willis equations, Metamaterials, Pre-stresses, Experiment, Identification

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we will firstly give an experimental illustration that the static Willis-form equations can simultaneously explain the stress-stiffening and the spin-softening effect of a rotational heavy spring. Thus it gives an experimental evidence of the validity of the Willis-form equations. Then, a full-wave inversion method is proposed to identify the initial normal stresses through the thickness of a plate, based on these equations. Experimental results are also presented to demonstrate its validity and performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over three decades ago, Professor Willis proposed a new set of linear elastodynamic equations for inhomogeneous media [1]. These equations are featured with additional velocity coupling terms as:

$$\langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle = \mathbf{C}_{eff} \langle \mathbf{e} \rangle + \mathbf{S}_{eff} \langle \dot{\mathbf{u}} \rangle \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \langle \boldsymbol{\sigma} \rangle + \mathbf{f} = \bar{\mathbf{S}}_{eff} \langle \dot{\mathbf{e}} \rangle + \boldsymbol{\rho}_{eff} \langle \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \rangle \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress tensor; \mathbf{u} is the displacement vector free of rigid translations; \mathbf{e} is the small strain tensor; \mathbf{f} is the body force vector; $\langle \ \rangle$ denotes the ensemble average; the superposed dot denotes the differentiation with respect to time t ; \mathbf{C}_{eff} , \mathbf{S}_{eff} , $\bar{\mathbf{S}}_{eff}$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{eff}$ are non-local operators. However, these equations had not been drawn much attention until the upsurge of designing metamaterials with transformation methods [2].

By using the transformation method, Milton et al. found that the classical linear elastic equations in frequency domain are not form-invariant and will change to the corresponding local Willis equations after the transformation [3]. Later on, Xiang and Yao found their corresponding forms in time domain, which involve the gradient of pre-stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0 \nabla$ [4, 5]:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} : \nabla \mathbf{u} + (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0 \nabla) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (3)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \mathbf{f} = (\boldsymbol{\sigma}^0 \nabla)^T : \nabla \mathbf{u} + [(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^0) \nabla] \cdot \mathbf{u} + \boldsymbol{\rho} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{u}} \quad (4)$$

Compared with classical linear elasticity equations, the above equations are new and hence must be experimentally verified before their implementations. For this purpose, we will briefly introduce an experimental evidence of the static Willis-form equations with displacement coupling terms [6]. With

the confidence of this verification, an inversion method is introduced to identify the initial normal stresses through the thickness of a plate.

2 THE ROTATIONAL HEAVY SPRING EXPERIMENT

Figure 1: A heavy soft spring with end pull force under steady rotation.

It is noticed from Eqs. (3) and (4) that the Willis-form equations involve the incremental Cauchy stress of a material point from the pre-stressed configuration B^0 to the perturbed configuration B^1 . Therefore, an experiment of a rotational heavy soft spring in Figure 1 is suitable to check the validity of these equations, because in this case the pretension inside the spring can be clearly calculated.

2.1 Theories

As shown in Figure 1, a rigid bar of length c connects the rotation centre o with a uniform helical spring of total mass M , unstretched length L and spring constant K . The whole system rotates at a constant angular velocity ω . The spring end is subjected to a pull force f , which can be conveniently generated by attaching an end mass M^a in the experiment as $f = M^a \omega^2 (c + R + d)$, where d is the distance between the outer end of the spring and the mass center.

Regardless of the influences from friction, gravitational force and lateral bending, one can obtain the position of the deformed spring at a material (Lagrangian) coordinate m ($0 \leq m \leq M$) [6]:

$$r(m) = \left[\frac{f + KL}{Kq \cos(q)} + c \tan(q) \right] \sin\left(\frac{q}{M} m\right) + c \left[\cos\left(\frac{q}{M} m\right) - 1 \right] \quad (5)$$

and the corresponding tensile force:

$$F(m) = \left[\frac{f + KL}{\cos(q)} + cKq \tan(q) \right] \cos\left(\frac{q}{M} m\right) - cKq \sin\left(\frac{q}{M} m\right) - KL \quad (6)$$

where

$$q = \omega \sqrt{\frac{M}{K}} \quad (7)$$

Let us examine the perturbation from B^0 to B^1 , when the end pull force changes from f^0 to $f^1 = f^0 + \Delta f$. After this perturbation, the position of this material point changes from r^0 to $r^1 = r^0 + u$, and the corresponding tensile force changes from F^0 to $F^1 = F^0 + \Delta F$.

Based on Eqs. (5) and (6), one can obtain the constitutive relation [6]:

$$\Delta F = K_\omega u = \left[K_t + \frac{dF^0(r^0)}{dr^0} \right] u \quad (8)$$

where the effective and tangent spring constants are

$$K_{\omega} = q \cot\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right)K \text{ and } K_t = \frac{\frac{f^0 + KL}{Kq \cos(q)} + c \tan(q)}{\frac{f^0 + KL}{Kq \cos(q)} + c \left[\tan(q) - \tan\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right) \right] \sin\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right) \cos\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right)} \frac{qK}{}, \quad (9)$$

respectively. Denoting the cross-sectional area of this spring as A and $\sigma = \Delta F / A$, $\sigma^0 = F^0 / A$, Eq. (8) can be rewritten in the Willis-form as:

$$\sigma = C^0 e + \frac{d\sigma^0}{dr^0} u \quad (10)$$

where

$$C^0 = \frac{f^0 + KL + cKq \sin(q)}{A \cos(q) \cos\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right)} \quad (11a)$$

$$e = B(f^0) \frac{q}{M} \cot\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right) u \quad (11b)$$

$$B(f) = \frac{1}{\left[\frac{f + KL}{Kq \cos(q)} + c \tan(q) \right] \cos\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right) \frac{q}{M} - c \sin\left(\frac{q}{M}m\right) \frac{q}{M}} \quad (11c)$$

One can also obtain the equation of motion from Eqs. (5) and (6) as [6]:

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dr^0} \approx 2 \frac{d\sigma^0}{dr^0} e + \frac{d^2 \sigma^0}{(dr^0)^2} u \quad (12)$$

which is the 1D static version of Eq. (4).

2.2 Experimental results

A stainless steel spring of $M = 12.83\text{g}$, $L = 201.0\text{mm}$ and $K = 4.64\text{N/m}$ was tested in the experiment with $c = 64.5\text{mm}$. Two end masses of $M^a = 2.37\text{g}$ and $M^a = 4.75\text{g}$ with the same $d = 8\text{mm}$ are used to generate end pull force f^0 and f^1 , respectively.

Figure 2: The comparison of deformed length R .

Figure 3: K_{ω} at the spring end with $M^a = 2.37\text{g}$.

As Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows, the experimental measurements agree with the theoretical predictions very well. This confirms the validity of Eqs. (5) and (6). Hence, the Willis-form equations (10) and (12) are verified indirectly.

Figure 4: K_ω , K_t and dF^0/dr^0 at the spring end with $M^a = 2.37g$.

In addition, since the tensile force increases along with the rotational velocity, one should observe the stress-stiffening effect. However, Figure 3 only shows a clear spin-softening effect. To clarify this problem, we plot K_ω , K_t and dF^0/dr^0 separately in Figure 4. It observes that with the increase of ω , the tangent spring constant K_t does increase, which represents the stress-stiffening effect; while the decrease of dF^0/dr^0 represents the spin-softening effect. Because the decrease of dF^0/dr^0 dominates the increase of K_t , the synthetic effect is the decrease of K_ω , i.e., the spin-softening effect. These observations give a strong support of the validity of the Willis-form equations, in which dF^0/dr^0 plays an important role to naturally describe the spin-softening effect.

3 IDENTIFICATION OF INITIAL STRESSES

With the confidence obtained from the above experimental results, we try to develop new method to identify initial stresses, because the Willis-form equations explicitly contain their gradients.

Figure 5: Testing model.

As Figure 5 shows, we can use the 1D Willis-form equations to describe the propagation of the ultrasound inside a plate. Then, we can try to identify the gradient of the initial stresses through the thickness of the plate from the measured ultrasound signals and finally obtain the initial stresses by integration.

3.1 The direct problem

Considering the damping effect, the finite element formulation of the 1D version of Eqs. (4) and (5) free of body force can be written as:

$$M\ddot{V} + c\dot{V} + KV = 0 \quad (13)$$

where V is the nodal voltage vector that is proportional to the nodal displacement vector \mathbf{a} , and

$$\mathbf{M} = \sum \mathbf{M}^e \quad \mathbf{M}^e = \int_e \rho \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} dx \quad (14a)$$

$$\mathbf{c} = \sum \mathbf{c}^e \quad \mathbf{c}^e = \int_e \mu \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{N} dx \quad (14b)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum \mathbf{K}^e \quad \mathbf{K}^e = \int_e \left[\kappa \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B} + \chi (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{N} + \mathbf{N}^T \mathbf{B}) \right] dx \quad \mathbf{B} = \partial \mathbf{N} / \partial x \quad (14c)$$

N is the trial function of 1D spectral element with five Gauss-Lobatto-Legendre integration points [7]. κ is the stiffness parameter. μ is the damping coefficient. $\chi = d\sigma^0 / dx$ is the gradient of initial normal stress σ^0 . One can easily find from Eq. (14c) that χ acts as an effective stiffness parameter, which is assumed to be a constant within a small element and thus χ' , the second right-hand term of Eq. (4), can be ignored. Eq. (13) can be efficiently solved by using the Central Difference Method (CDM).

3.2 The inverse problem

Based on Eq. (13), the vector of n parameters \mathbf{p} can be identified by using the Gauss-Newton method to minimize the residual $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{S}(\mathbf{V}^* - \mathbf{V})$, where \mathbf{V}^* is the measured voltage and \mathbf{S} is a selective matrix that determines the time interval of the measurement. This parameter identification procedure can be iteratively conducted as $\mathbf{p}^k = \mathbf{p}^{k-1} + \Delta \mathbf{p}^{k-1}$, ($k = 1, 2, \dots$) until $average(\|\Delta \mathbf{p}_i^{k-1} / p_i^k\|) < 0.01$. The incremental parameter vector is:

$$\Delta \mathbf{p}^{k-1} = \min \left\{ \left\| \mathbf{J}^{k-1} \Delta \mathbf{p}^{k-1} - \mathbf{R}^{k-1} \right\|_2 + \alpha \left\| \Delta \mathbf{p}^{k-1} \right\|_m^m \right\} = - \left[(\mathbf{J}^{k-1})^T \mathbf{J}^{k-1} + \boldsymbol{\beta}^{k-1} \right]^{-1} (\mathbf{J}^{k-1})^T \mathbf{R}^{k-1} \quad (15)$$

where, $\mathbf{J} = \partial \mathbf{V} / \partial \mathbf{p}$; α is a Tikhonov regularization parameter, which is determined by the L-curve method [8] in this paper; the regularization matrix $\boldsymbol{\beta}^{k-1}$ is a diagonal matrix that is defined as $\beta_i^{k-1} = \alpha w_i^{k-1} \max \left\{ (\mathbf{J}^{k-1})^T \mathbf{J}^{k-1} \right\}$; and w_i^{k-1} is a weighting coefficient [9]:

$$\left\| \Delta \mathbf{p}^{k-1} \right\|_m^m = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i^{k-1} (\Delta p_i^{k-1})^2 \quad w_i^{k-1} = \begin{cases} 1 & m = 2 \text{ or } k = 1 \\ \frac{1}{|\Delta p_i^{k-1}| + 0.001} & m = 1 \text{ and } k > 1 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where $m = 2$ means to use the L_2 -norm regularization to obtain smoothly distributed parameters; and $m = 1$ means to use the L_1 -norm regularization to obtain sparse solutions. However, since the interested parameter χ could be local-smoothly distributed near the plate surface, the *quasi-sparse regularization* should be adopted, in which $m = 1$ and the diagonal elements of $\boldsymbol{\beta}^{k-1}$ are rescaled by a factor to ensure $\min \left\{ \beta_i^{k-1} \right\} = \alpha \max \left\{ (\mathbf{J}^{k-1})^T \mathbf{J}^{k-1} \right\}$.

3.3 Testing results

A PMMA plate of 2.5mm thickness and 50mm in diameter was tested in the experiment. A transducer of 10MHz central frequency was used to incident ultrasound pulses into the plate and to receive the echoed signals. The contact pressure between this transducer and the plate surface was about 62kPa. An oscilloscope with the sampling frequency of 1GHz was used to record the signals.

The finite element model contains 200 elements uniformly distributed through the thickness of the plate; so that the length of each element is only 12.5 μ m. 1ns time step was adopted to solve Eq. (13) by the CDM. It assumes that κ , μ and ρ are the same in all elements, and only χ is different in each element. Since ρ can be reliably determined as 1190kg/m³, there are 202 parameters should be

identified in two steps. The first step identifies only κ and μ while keep $\chi = 0$ by using L_2 -norm regularization. Then, the obtained values of κ and μ are fixed and only χ are identified in the second step by using quasi-sparse regularization. Finally, the distribution of initial stresses can be obtained by integrating the identified distribution of χ .

Figure 6: The identified results.

The transducer was placed on each side of the plate, respectively, to test the repeatability of the measurement. Figure 6 shows the identified results, which are reasonable due to the following observations:

- (1) the distribution of χ is nearly asymmetric about the middle layer of the plate. This coincides with the nearly symmetrically distributed initial normal stresses.
- (2) the identified χ and the initial normal stress near Side 2 are always larger than those near Side 1, no matter the transducer is put on Side 1 or Side 2. This implies that the identified results is independent of the position of the transducer.
- (3) the identified initial normal stresses on the incident surface of the transducer are close to theoretical pressure of 62kPa.
- (4) the distribution of the initial normal stresses concentrate near the two surfaces of the plate.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary experiment evidence presented in this paper gives us much confidence on the validity of the Willis-form equations. Although the coupling terms in these equations are usually very weak for macro structures, they could have much impact on the structures of small sizes, such as the surface/interfaces. In this sense, the Willis-form equations have great application potentials. One example is the inversion method presented in this paper, which can achieve $12.5\mu\text{m}$ sub-wave length spatial resolution and at least 0.1MPa accuracy. This ability is very competitive to existing initial stress identification techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the National Science Foundation of China [grant numbers 11672144, 11272168].

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